

Drought resistance

IR5178-1-1-4, an outstanding drought-tolerant line

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Moisture level and stress affect the performance of rice. In 1979, reduced rainfall at the RRS, Nagina U.P., lasted 88 days. The normal rainfall during the monsoon season is 800 mm, but in 1979, only 337.5 mm was recorded. Between 25 July and 20 October only 27 mm of rain fell.

During 1979 kharif, the International Upland Rice Yield Nursery (IURYN) seeds were sown on 29 June. Nagina 22 was sown as a local check. Only two varieties, IR5178-1-1-4 and Nagina 22 flowered and set seed (see photo). They produced yields of 1.43 and 0.27 t/ha, respectively (see table). The non-flowering varieties dried up.

The crop did not suffer from moisture stress during the first 26 days of the drought (29 Jun - 25 Jul); therefore, crop establishment was good. But moisture stress was acute after that period.

The performance of IR5178-1-1-4 under acute moisture stress was remarkable. The mechanism of its drought tolerance needs investigation. ■

Nagina scientists at IURYN plot. Rice breeder points out the seeded variety.

Performance of IR5178-1-1-4 and the check Nagina 22 in the IURYN. Rice Research Station, Nagina, India, 1979.

Variety	Days to heading	Days to maturity	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR5178-1-1-4	57	88	85.2	18.1	1.43
Nagina 22	81	109	58.1	16.4	0.27

Temperature tolerance

Thermosensitivity of aus and boro varieties of Bangladesh

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Aus and boro varieties are photoperiod-insensitive rice groups of Bangladesh. They have been cultivated for centuries under distinct ecological conditions. The

vegetative, reproductive, and ripening phases of aus varieties always experience high temperature but the greater part of the life cycle of boro varieties is subject to cold temperature.

To determine whether the two rice groups are really distinct ecotypes in terms of thermosensitivity, 40-day-old seedlings of 80 boro and 133 aus varieties were transplanted in January 1978 in a puddled field. There were 2

seedlings/hill spaced 25 × 15 cm. The tillering potentiality in cold temperature was used as an index of thermosensitivity and measured as relative tillering rate (RTR):

$$\text{RTR} = \frac{\text{Final tiller} - \text{initial tiller number}}{\text{Initial tiller number}}$$

The RTR of all test materials was computed 30 days after transplanting

(DT), the coldest period during their tillering stage. The minimum temperature varied between 9.1°C and 14.5°C, and the mean temperature, between 14.8°C and 20.65°C. More than 90% of the aus entries had from negative to 0.59 RTR, but more than 90% of the boro were in the range of 0.10 to 1.59 (see figure). Negative to zero RTR indicated either failure to survive or no tiller production.

To compare tillering potentiality by group, the average RTR values of 50 aus and 50 boro varieties were determined at 10-day intervals up to 50 DT. During the 30-day period after transplanting, the boro varieties had 3 times higher RTR values, indicating their better adaptability to cold temperature. From 30 to 50 DT, the RTR values of the two groups were similar. The temperature during this period was higher than that of the 30-day period after transplanting.

Thus, the two traditional rice groups

may be considered as two ecotypes. Perhaps, during the evolution process, only the boro varieties of the

photoperiod-insensitive rice groups of Bangladesh became adapted to cold climates through natural selection. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Severe blast outbreak during 1979-80 boro in Bangladesh

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About a decade ago, blast was a major rice disease in Bangladesh. But with changes in cultivation patterns, the introduction of improved blast-resistant varieties, and changes from rainfed to irrigated culture disease incidence has remained low since 1968.

During the 1980 boro (Nov. 1979-May 1980), however, blast broke out in almost all regions of Bangladesh. Chandina, IR8, Pajam, and Pusa II were attacked (see table). Attacks on BR3, BR6, BR7, and Purbachi were, however, mild. BR8, BR9, and Pajam also had neck blast. No indigenous variety was infected. Severe infection destroyed fields of Pajam in Dacca and Sylhet areas; fields of Chandina, Pajam, and Pusa-II in Comilla; and fields of IR8 and Pajam

Incidence of blast during 1979-80 boro in some areas of Bangladesh.

Area	Blast difference ^a on different varieties						
	Chan-dina	IR8	Pajam II	Pusa II	Pur-bachi	Other improved varieties ^b	Local
Barisal	-	VS	L	-	M	L	N
Chittagong	L	VS	S	-	L	L	N
Comilla	VS	L	S	VS	L	L	N
Dacca	L	L	VS	-	L	L	N
Sylhet	L	L	S	-	L	L	N
Northern districts	L	L	L	-	L	L	L

^aVS = very severe (disease incidence [DI] 7-9), S = severe (DI 5-7), M = moderate (DI 3-5), L = low (DI 1-3), N = nil. A dash (-) means the variety is not grown in the area. ^bInclude BR3, BR6, BR7, BR8, and BR9.

in Barisal and Chittagong. At the Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra (DND) project area, IR8 was infected only in plots severely attacked by ufra nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*. In the north and northwest, only mild and scattered infections were observed but in east, south-east, and central Bangladesh the incidence was severe.

The following factors were considered favorable for the development of blast disease during that season:

1. From October 1979 to April 1980 there was low night (10-25°C) and high day (24-25°C) temperatures.

2. The relative humidity of the atmosphere was high (92-95% at 0600 and 44-77% at 1200) during this period.

3. Dew formation on leaves was quite heavy at night during those months.

4. The affected plots were mostly dry because of scanty irrigation water during early crop growth.

5. The affected fields were mostly at